

SYNTHESIS OF CARBON NANOTUBES AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CNTs/ PHENOLIC COMPOSITES

Nyan-Hwa Tai⁺, Meng-Kao Yeh[□], Chia-Hao Liu[□], Hsiang-Ming Hsueh[□], Chan-hsin Yang[□]

[□]Department of Materials Science and Engineering

[□]Department of Power Mechanical Engineering

National Tsing-Hua University, Hsin-Chu, Taiwan, ROC, 30013

⁺nhtai@mse.nthu.edu.tw

SUMMARY: Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) were synthesized through the floating catalyst chemical vapor deposition process. The as-fabricated MWNTs (5% by weight) were then introduced into phenolic resin as the reinforcement of the MWNTs/phenolic composites. Raman spectroscopy was adopted to investigate the microstructure of the synthesized MWNTs; and mechanical properties such as tensile strength, Young's modulus, and Poisson's ratio were measured. Morphologies of the as-fabricated MWNTs and microstructure of the fracture surface of the composites were examined by field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM).

KEYWORDS: Multi-walled carbon nanotubes, Composites, Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD)

INTRODUCTION

Since the discovery of carbon nanotubes in 1991 by Iijima[1], numerous investigations have been reported on the study of applications of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in engineering during the past decade. Due to the unique electronic, mechanical, and physical properties, CNTs offer superior potential for the development of new applications and new materials systems. It was reported that with the superior properties CNTs can be used in hydrogen storage, Li-ion battery, flat panel display, chemical sensor, single electronic device, SPM probe, and composites etc [2-7].

On the synthesis of CNTs, three primary routes, including arc-discharge, laser ablation, and chemical vapor deposition, were proposed [8-10]. Among these three routes for fabricating carbon nanotubes, the chemical vapor deposition method is the most promising route for mass production of CNTs. Once the mass-production method for producing high quality CNTs is developed, the applications of CNTs in engineering become feasible.

Numerous articles revealed that CNTs have superior mechanical properties; for example, the tensile modulus over 1.0 TPa, the tensile strength over 50 MPa, and the failure strain in the range between 0.05 ~ 0.1 were reported[11]. However, some of the articles reported that the improvement in mechanical properties of CNTs/polymer composites is very limited. The performance of CNTs reinforced polymeric composites was affected very significantly by the fabrication route. Besides raw materials, uniform dispersion, well alignment of CNTs within composites, and strong interfacial strength are three primary parameters for obtaining high performance composites. In this study, MWNTs were synthesized by the chemical vapor deposition method in a tube furnace. The as-fabricated CNTs were then introduced to phenolic resin for making CNTs/phenolic composites. Mechanical properties and morphologies of the synthesized MWNTs and microstructure of the fracture surface of the composites were examined by FEGSEM.

EXPERIMENTAL

SYNTHESIS OF MWNTS

In this study, benzene, ferrocene, and hydrogen were adopted as carbon precursor gas, catalyst, and buffer gas, respectively. CNTs with the diameter distribution within 50 nm were synthesized. For producing high quality MWNTs, the floating catalyst method was adopted. The apparatus of the experiment is shown in Figure 1. Hydrogen controlled by mass flow meters (MFC1/MFC2) was

served as buffer gas. Benzene mixed with thiophene (with the ratio of 0.13/30) was placed in glass container as the carbon precursor. Hydrogen passed through MFC2 and bubbled the carbon precursor. The precursor evaporated ferrocene (at 90°C) and then channeled into the reaction furnace for carbon nanotube fabrication. At the temperature of 1150°C, the reactant(s) decompose for forming MWNTs. In this process, the temperature for ferrocene evaporation plays an important role on the synthesis of CNTs. Too high the temperature, rapid evaporation in ferrocene produces larger cluster, which induces larger diameter CNTs; as a results, uniform distribution in CNTs diameter is difficult to obtain. When the experiment came to the end, the CNT products were collected from the furnace wall. In this study, 2.82 g CNTs can be obtained for the processing time of 120 minutes.

Figure 1. Schematic figure of the set-up for the synthesis of carbon nanotubes by the floating catalyst method

PREPARATION OF NANOCOMPOSITE SPECIMENS

The matrix used for the fabrication of nanocomposite was resol type phenolic PF-650 resin. The CNTs were dispersed in solvent and mixed with phenolic resin in a magnetic stirred container for 3 hours, after sufficient mixing, the CNTs-phenolic mixture was put in an oven at 90°C for 3-4 hours to evaporate methanol. The evaporated mixture was then compression molded at a pressure of 1300 psi and temperature of 160°C for 2 hours. After natural cooling, the nanocomposites were cut into $60 \times 16 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ specimens and end tabs were glued on both ends of the specimen for mechanical testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FESEM image of the MWNTs synthesized from the floating catalyst method was shown in Figure 2. It can be detected that the products contain very few impurity. The amorphous particles shown in the figure may be caused by the incomplete reduction of catalyst particles. The length of MWNT is more than 10 μm and the diameter is less than 50 nm.

Figure 2 FEGSEM of the as-fabricated CNTs .

The Raman spectrum of the as-fabricated MWNTs, as shown in Figure 3, reveals that the MWNTs is highly graphitized ($I_D/I_G = 0.45$) carbon material. Based upon the SEM image and Raman the spectrum, it is no doubt that the MWNTs used in this study have a superior property in microstructure with highly purity.

On the testing of mechanical properties, the nanocomposite specimens were clamped properly on a self-made tensile testing machine at room temperature. The load cell signal gave the tensile load, which resulted in the engineering stress for the specimen. The corresponding strain was measured using resistance strain gauges, bonded to the surface of the specimens at the middle region.

Figure 4 shows the stress-strain curves for the 5 wt% MWNT/phenolic nanocomposite and the pure phenolic specimens. The Young's modulus is 2.58 GPa, the yield stress 19.49 MPa and the Poisson's ratio 0.376 for composites and the Young's modulus is 2.16 GPa, the yield stress 16.50 MPa, and Poisson's ratio 0.417 for pure phenolic. Tensile tests on the MWNT/phenolic nanocomposite show that the introducing of 5 wt% MWNT to phenolic resin results in 19.4% and 18.1% increases in Young's modulus and yield stress, respectively, and 9.8% decrease in Poisson's ratio (as shown in Figure 5). The decrease in Poisson's ratio is attributed to the restriction of CNTs on the lateral contraction during tensile test. Typical Young's modulus and tensile strength of pure phenolic are 4.4 GPa and 50~60 MPa, respectively[12]. The lower mechanical properties shown in this work indicates that the experimental parameters adopted in this study are not optimized. However, the reinforcing effect by the CNTs do enhance the tensile strength and Young's modulus.

FESEM was used to examine the morphologies of the fracture surface. As shown in Figure 6, smooth and flake-like fracture surface indicates that brittle fracture occurs during failure. Moreover, small holes and upward reinforcements, as indicated by A and B in Figure 8, respectively, depicts the pull-out of CNTs from matrix during testing. The smooth surface on the pulled-out CNT implies weak interfacial strength between CNTs and phenolic matrix; as a result, fracture front propagates along the interface. From the SEM image, it is observed that the MWNTs were randomly dispersed in matrix in local area. However, non-uniform dispersion of CNTs within matrix is also detected on the fracture surface (which is not shown in this text).

Figure 4 The stress-strain curves of the pure phenolic and the nanocomposites

Figure 5 Variation of axial and lateral strain of the pure phenolic and the nanocomposites

Figure 6 Morphology on the fracture surface of the MWNT/phenolic composites under tension

CONCLUSIONS

Phenolic reinforced by CNTs composite was fabricated in this work. MWNTs synthesized from the floating catalyst chemical vapor deposition process were adopted as the reinforcement. Uniform distribution in diameter of the MWNTs was obtained from the CVD process. Young's modulus and tensile strength were enhanced over 18 % once 5 wt% MWNTs were introduced into the matrix. Morphologies on the fracture surface indicate brittle fracture, and smooth CNT surface implies weak interfacial bonding between reinforcement and matrix.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support for this work by National Science Council under the contract No: NSC-91-2120-E-007-004 and Ministry of Education of Republic of China under the contract No: A-91-E- FA04-1-4.

REFERENCES

1. Iijima S. Helical Microtubes of Graphitic Carbon, *Nature*, V. 354, 56-58 (1991).
2. Y. Chen, D.T. Shaw, X.D. Bai, E.G. Wang, C. Lund, W.M. Lu, and D.D.L. Chung, Hydrogen Storage in Aligned Carbon Nanotubes, *Applied Physics Letters*, . 78, No. 15, 2128-2130 (2001).
3. H. Shimoda, B. Gao, X.P. Tang, A. Kleinhammes, L. Fleming, Y. Wu, and O. Zhou, Lithium Intercalation into Opened Single-wall Carbon Nanotubes:Storage Capacity and Electronic Properties, *Physical Review Letters*, V. 88, N. 1, 015502-1~4(2001).
4. S. Fan, M.G. Chapline, N.R. Franklin, T.W. Ombler, A.M. Cassell, and H. Dai, Self-oriented Regular Arrays of Carbon Nanotubes and Their Field Emission Properties, *Science*, Vol. 283, 512-514 (1999).
5. S.J. Tans, A.R.M. Verschueren , and C. Dekker, Room-temperature Transistor Based on a Single Carbon Nanotubes, *Nature*, V. 393, 49-51 (1998).
6. S.S. Wong, E. Joselevich, A.T. Woolley, C.L. Cheung, and C.M. Lieber, Covalently Functionalized Nanotubes as Nanometre-sized Probes in Chemistry and Biology, *Nature*, V. 394, 52-55(1998).
7. Erik T. Thostenson, Zhifeng Ren, and Tsu-Wei Chou, *Advances in the Science and Technology of*

Carbon nanotubes and Their Composites: A Review, *Composites Science and Technology*, V.61, 1899-1912 (2001).

8. Z. Shi, Y.Lian, X. Zhou, Z. Gu, Y. Zhang, S. Iijima, L Zhou, K.T. Yue, and S. Zhang, Mass-production of Single-wall Carbon Nanotubes by Arc-discharge Method, *Carbon*, V. 37, 1449-1453 (1999).
9. W.K. Maser, E. Munoz, A.M. enito, M. T. Martinez, G.F. de la Fuente, Y. Maniette, E. Anglaret, and J.L. Sauvajol, Production of High-density Single-Walled nanotube Material by a Simple Laser-Ablation Method, *Chemical Physics Letters*, .292, 587-593, (1998).
- 10 H.W. Zhu, C.L. Xu, D.H. Wu, B.Q. Wei, R. Vajtai, and P.M. Ajayan, Direct Synthesis of Long Single-Walled Carbon Nanotube Strands, *Science*, V. 296, 884-886 (2002)
- 11.S. Kita, H. Nishijima, and Y. Nakayama, Influence of Stiffness of Carbon-nanotube Probes in Atomic Force Microscopy, *J. Phys. D: Apply Physics*, V.33, 2673-2677 (2000)
12. F.L. Matthews and R.D. Rawlings, *Composite Materials: Engineering and Science*, Chapman & Hall, New York, (1994).